

ATHENA - An Interactive Shop System

Anna Bazmajyan
University of Bonn
s6anbazm@uni-bonn.de

Behnam Ghavimi
University of Bonn
ghavimi@iai.uni-bonn.de

Helma Torkamaan
University of Bonn
h.torkamaan@uni-bonn.de

Urmimala Majumdar
RWTH Aachen University
urmimala.majumdar@rwth-aachen.de

ABSTRACT

We are in an age of unprecedented growth of communication and computing technologies with a wide variety of interactive systems. Mostly retails chains and stores employ such systems for online shopping and increasing their user base. However, there exists also a need or scope for providing entertainment in a shopping atmosphere with the two-fold objective of advertising and enhancing brand value. This paper describes our efforts, approach and techniques used to design, realize and test a system (named Athena) which can address such a need.

Keywords

User Centered Technology Design, Interactive System, entertainment shopping, ATHENA

1. INTRODUCTION

Interactive systems have been employed by shops and retail outlets inside the shop and also outside it - as part of the shop window or another system. The motivation for the introduction of an interactive system in a shop environment is coupled with the different tasks and goals of various people associated with the shop. Our research and observation shows that while most customers inside the shop are there with the aim of purchasing some item, the ones outside i.e. the potential customers or passersby glance into the shop with the objective of getting informed about the different offers and items inside the store. Keeping these in mind interactive systems can serve several purposes such as - increase sales by providing more shopping options to the customers, advertising by showcasing latest products and discounts, attracting more customers with services like virtual changing rooms, and increasing brand value or enhancing store image.

We started out by exploring ideas about interactive shop window systems. However, study results in [3] prompted us to believe that there were more opportunities to explore with in-store interactive systems. The research demonstrates that the in-store billboards affect the store image and sale more than window displays, and consequently we decided to change our focus. We were initially concentrating on a system addressing need for knowing different fashion and style ideas. Anyhow, after few rounds of user interviews, based on our users' preference, we resolved to deal with the need for entertainment for people who accompany others during shopping. This idea serves the two-fold purpose of advertising and enhancing brand value of the shop.

In this paper we have attempted to present all the work related to our project. We will first take up the analysis of design and technology, in which there will be a discussion on the current design, the focus group for the project, the technology requirements and then the overall requirements of the project. This will be followed by a detailed review of the various prototypes and user reviews of the same. Finally, we will submit a list of ideas for the future work on the system.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Initial Research and Insights

From the research papers [1, 2, 4, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 17, 16, 18, 19, 20, 22, 23, 24, 25] we gained related knowledge which may be grouped as follows.

- Marketing and shopping related information and research results
- Standards and guidelines for internal design, artistic design and architecture
- Analysis of psychological research and studies on user behaviors with focus on shopping and customer behavior
- Design techniques related information and research results

From all the read information we understand that there are many factors effective on customers' decision for going to a

specific shop. Some of these factors are store name, atmosphere, previous experience, popularity among population, etc. and in general term store image for the customers. The element effective on shop personality or image, the effect of different implementations of these elements on customer, sale, and totally on shop image have been studied widely. Music, design, architecture, lighting, advertising, models dressing, shelves ordering and organizing, service, accessibilities, facilities, temperate, color and several other factors are all effective. There are also researches on product related studies that state based on the type of product presented in the shops, the behavior, and the effect of these elements on shop image and personalities might be different.

Based on the market research and the amount of money and time that people spent in the market in a year and considering the users opinion about shopping, clothing, styling and based on the yearly regional and global reports on shopping details and market value, it became obvious that the best industry to focus considering project goal is clothing.

2.2 Existing Systems for Virtual Dressing Rooms

We searched for systems with similar ideas or activities that might be potential competitors for us. There were many systems in the market trying to present similar background ideas to our systems, however majority of these system were focusing on online shop systems. Most of them are not working inside the shops even if they had the capability to do so by some changes. Here we will present some of our major competitors:

2.2.1 Styku

Styku [21] scans body of the user in a blink of an eye, makes a 3D model of his/her body and saves it in the system. This idea can help user to buy clothes online by very accurate size based on the 3D model. This system has some pros and cons like all the other systems. In comparison to similar systems, it is cheaper and faster. Further it is more accurate due to its use of approximately 4 Kinects for scanning user's body. However, it doesn't consider the variable size of user and continues to focus on online shopping.

Figure 1: Styku

2.2.2 Fits

Fits [6] is a kind of plug-in for online shops. Users should at first fill out a form about their sizes and then based on these sizes, this site can help user to choose a clothes with correct

sizes. This system has a huge database which is generated by two robotic mannequins. These two mannequins make all different sizes which are possible for all clothes and the results are saved in the database. Also the general idea seems to be subtle but it appear to have some flaws such as not considering the color of skin and the other elements which can have influence on user's decision. They just focus on the online shop and they are not interested about the environment inside the shops.

Figure 2: Fits

2.2.3 Glamstorm

This system [8] follows a very naive idea. There is a static picture of a girl model as the main character. The user can choose items that she wants to buy and items will be shown on that model. It is kind of multi-layer picture which in the first layer you have that model and by adding the other items you will add the other layers on that first picture. It doesn't have any special functionality with great benefits. But from the user perspective it appear to be entertaining and perhaps result in longer usage of the system.

Figure 3: Glamstorm

2.2.4 FitYour

This system [7] is quite similar to Glamstorm system but it is an improvement. The FitYour team has tried to make their system an acceptable application for PC. This application captures user through the camera of a PC and shows that user on the screen. User can then add some items like shirt

to his or her pictures. This application is not so precise so it let user to resize that items or change place of that items on their pictures for finding best place and size for them.

2.2.5 *Fitnect and Nice.Interactive*

Fitnect [5] and Nice.Interactive [15] follow same idea as FitYour but the big difference is the usage of Kinect. These applications can be used in shops and then detect body of a user with Kinect. User can select some items and then these applications project these items on the picture of the user. Anyhow we observed that even by using Kinect the result is not that realistic but it is more precise than its competitors. These systems can not only serve as virtual mirror but also in some cases they are used as an entertaining device in the shops.

Figure 4: Fitnect

3. DESIGN & TECHNOLOGY

3.1 Current Design

We started with brainstorming and then creating textual scenarios of our system. During the second iteration we created initial storyboards, which was combination of our all ideas related to the virtual dressing room.

After observing the general Spaces of Opportunities, conducting 3 long user interviews, 668 user observations, and 11 detailed shadowing and interviews, we came up with 6 different ideas, which will be discussed in detail later on. Based on 5 long interviews and 33 participant survey results we chose Football as final idea to work on further.

During next iterations, we have created some versions of paper prototype using "Wizard of Oz" technique. Later we improved graphical design of our System. Finally, we used Kinect and "Wizard of Oz" to create our higher medium fidelity prototype.

3.2 System Requirements

3.2.1 *Functional Requirements*

Here are some of the requirements:

1. System should show screen crack effect when a person walks inside the sense range.
2. System should detect when the user walks outside the sense range after interaction.

3. System should reset the game stats when one user walks out of the sense range.
4. System should differentiate between two users.
5. System should be able to capture user movement made for kicking the ball.
6. System should provide demonstration to play the game.
7. System should be able to sense the presence of the person in the sense range.
8. System should show the screen saver when nobody is in that zone.
9. System should show the demo before the menu
10. System should update the score after each kick
11. System repeats the demo if there is no interaction after entering the zone.
12. System should show screen saver if the person doesn't choose any menu option.
13. Direction of the ball should be proportional to the direction of the kick.

3.2.2 *Non Functional Requirements*

14. System should have a maximum game playtime of 3 minutes.
15. The safe distance between the system and user should be minimum 1 m.
16. System should have the sense range of 1.5 m.
17. The option of kicking is five times.
18. System shows the demo 2 times in the case of 11th requirement.
19. System should show screen saver after 1 minute in the case of 12th requirement.
20. System should be reset after 15 sec in the case of 3th requirement.
21. The safe distance between user and the System should be min. 1 meter.

3.2.3 *Rationale and description of some requirements*

1. Based on the User Task-flow Observation and Interviews with End-Users (an Interview with Parsa on 04.12.2013), we have conducted Requirement 15. Because social norms demand that the Companion communicates and is available for the person he/she is accompanying, it is necessary that System is not so engaging that Companion forgets true role.
2. Requirement 15 is a result of some observations and tests. This requirement is necessary to prevent accidentally kicking the system while making a kick movement.

3. Requirement 5 Is important while system should detect user movement, this is the way how the system interacts with users. After making kick the direction of the ball should be proportional to the direction of the kick.
4. We have some Dependencies among our requirements
 Req. 15 and 8 are dependent on 7
 Req. 18 is dependent on 11
 Req. 19 is dependent on 12
 Req. 20 is dependent on 2 and 3

The complete lists of requirements in the format of Volere Template are available in the BSCW

3.3 Technology Specification

To decide what technology should be used, we took both the advantages and disadvantages into consideration. We took special consideration to a couple of different attributes to make the input methods easier to compare to each other.

- Precision
- Interaction simplicity
- Satisfaction
- Implementation difficulty
- Being beautiful

We thought that precision was the most important factor, since we believed it to coincide with other factors, such as how fun or annoying the interaction would be. We do not like input solution that takes far more time to implement than others as we wanted to put more work into creating a good interaction than working on making a connection between application and input device work properly. We can divide Technology two parts that is software and hardware of our system.

3.3.1 Technology in Use Currently

We can categorize shops by different criterion. Here we will categorize them by pioneer shops in using technology and classic shops.

We can categorize most of the shops as classic shops without considering that they are big or small. The reason is that some of them use technology but this technology is not used in a creative way. Therefore, it means that they neglect this huge space of opportunities that is created by technology. From the aspect of Hardware in classic shops, generally they use it for attracting and keeping more customers for longer time inside the shop. The majority use some portable devices for managing stock. They use some display monitors and several cameras for monitoring customers and finally for accounting part they mostly use PC or special cashier machine.

From aspect of software common application in use were accounting, security monitoring and stock managing applications.

Also there are few pioneer shops in total but their number is increasing fast. The main reason is that owners of the classic shops understand that they should have something new to attract more customers in market competition. They are more eager to come to technology innovation fields, take some creative solutions, and add them to their business. The common technology we observed in pioneer shops were Wi-Fi and Bluetooth for interacting with user or sending them some information. The benefits of Wi-Fi and Bluetooth are that many people nowadays have smartphones or cellphones with Bluetooth ability. By using these two, you can have extra opportunity in design. These two have some problems as well such as security and privacy issues or high battery usage rate. Another hardware we observed were the cameras, which could be used as input method. The advantage of cameras is that they have low price and they are easy to install. It also has some disadvantages such as low accuracy and the need to develop more complex program. The other input device is Kinect, which is precise and not so expensive. Few years ago, it was hard to program it but now there are many libraries, which have made programming easier. There are many more hardware options in this area but for the last instance, we mention touch or multi-touch screens. This kind of screens let user interact with system easily and give them feeling which is very close to real world. It helps us to mix digital elements with physical actions perfectly and create a reality aspect. The problem is when someone interacts with the system; his or her body blocks the view of the other person during interaction session. For showing output, they mostly use monitors or projectors. Both of these devices have some pros and cons. Projectors are easy to setup and you don't need very huge space for that but hardly you can reach a good display with projectors as they have always shadowing problems and even the strongest one cannot project pictures perfectly in a bright room. On the other side, the cost of maintenance is very high. Monitors give us quite vast range of sizes or even you can merge different monitors to a unified display. Today's they are in a good point and even can provide 3D scenes.

It is obvious that a game for PCs can be created in different methods and tools same as all the other application. You can start from zero point and create all elements by yourself with a language like C++ but always you can find easier way. Some big companies and open source code society have made different tools and applications that can help you to create a game easily, faster and much more professionally. First option always is game engines. This following text is from Wikipedia that describe game engine well. "A game engine is a system designed for the creation and development of video games. The leading game engines provide a software framework that developers use to create games for video game consoles, mobile devices, and personal computers. The core functionality typically provided by a game engine includes a rendering engine (renderer) for 2D or 3D graphics, a physics engine or collision detection (and collision response), sound, scripting, animation, artificial intelligence, networking, streaming, memory management, threading, localization support, and a scene graph. The process of game development is often economized, in large part, by reusing/adapting the same game engine to create different games, or to make it easier to "port" games to multiple platforms."

Unity 3D is one of these engine games. It has two versions that are free and paid versions. The free version has also good functionality, you can start working with that easily, and for result, you can gain an acceptable game. The other benefits of using this tool are that most of Indie game groups support it so it is good news. Indie game groups make different common codes between projects and publish them freely. For example for connecting to Kinect, there are many free codes in the Internet.

The other tool, which mostly can be used and is not so cheap, is adobe game tools. Adobe company give programmers and game makers a package that includes Adobe Scout, Adobe Gaming SDK, Flash Builder, Flash Professional, Photoshop, Illustrator, Phonegap Build. We do not want explain each of this application but we can say that using the mixture of this applications gives strong power to game makers. As always, you lose something for gaining something else, it is true that you gain strong power with this package but it is expensive and need good skills to deal with these applications and making good result with them. A game, which is created with this package, has some features such as it does not need any fragmentation, it has good quality on different displays, it is portable and most important one, this game can be used on different platforms without changing codes or structures.

3.3.2 Hardware & Software for Athena

There are huge number of hardware and software that can be used. In this subsection at first we want to propose a list of hardware that we have decided to use as main configuration of our system and describe our reasons for choosing them. Secondly, we want to talk about the software aspect and then we will finish this section by explaining briefly about hardware and software that we use for our final prototype.

Following list contains hardware that we have decided to use for our final product:

- Kinect: We chose Kinect because it was easy to install and program for PCs. It works precisely and does not need any extra element to assist it for interacting such as special boots or gloves. It gives user feeling of joy because it is mixture of physical actions and digital elements perfectly.
- Monitor: Not only can it full fill our needs which is showing a display with a good quality in the most of conditions such as different brightness level of a room but also It can provide the other options for us such as 3D. Size of system can be customized easily and it does not make any special maintenance task furthermore.
- PC configuration: We can use simple PC configuration such as CPU, motherboard and graphics card. The benefits are that we don't need to design a new board for our system which can be so much complicated and we can customize it easily. It is not so expensive and can be designed in the different size. The other device can be connected to that easily. In future if something goes wrong with one part, it can be replaced easily.
- Ticket printer: We need a Ticket printer which is small and can print what we need, perhaps discount coupons, on a small piece of paper. It can be easily connected to our

system and it is cheap.

- Speaker: We should choose a set of speakers which is suitable for our shop and probably some shop owners want to customize the properties of the sounds which come out of that speaker. It is very easy to install and customize same as our the other devices. It has a very big range of prices which related to it's quality and functionality.

From aspect of software we vote for unity 3D because free version of that can fulfill all needs of a professional game and it will helps us in reducing the time of development of our final product so we can focus on making a smoother and much more perfect interaction surface and design.

After having this detailed explanation of technologies to be used in our system we would like to mention the technology used in our final prototype. We used a projector instead of monitor and we implemented the prototype in Visual studio. We programmed kinect and our main program using C# WPF and VB.net.

3.4 Focus Group

User involvement is a widely accepted principle in the development of usable and useful systems. However, in practice it is possible to involve only a limited number of users. Thus, participating users must be selected for different kinds of collaboration. Moreover, the involved users should represent the intended users of the system as closely as possible.

3.4.1 The Process of Identifying User Groups

In order to reach representative users, the most important user groups need to be identified and described. We chose method of identifying Focus groups suggested by Hackos and Redish [9]. The idea is to brainstorm preliminary list of users and create a matrix. Following steps need to be accomplished.

1. Brainstorm a preliminary list of users.
2. Describe the main user characteristics (including market size).
3. Define typical user and other users. Group by these characteristics
4. Describe main user groups and prioritize them
5. Select typical representative from the groups
6. Define tasks by each user group type

3.4.2 Preliminary Potential Users

As a result of brainstorming, statistics and market studies we have conducted following list of Preliminary users.

1. Clients
2. Shop Assistants
3. Technical Support
4. Need Based Shoppers

5. Fashion Lovers
6. Companion
7. Supporter
8. Shopper

3.4.3 Main User Characteristics

After brainstorming a list of users, it is important to identify their main characteristics. These characteristics help to identify the diversity of users and the groups they form. We have gathered main user characteristics from field studies, literature and brainstorming and categorized them as following.

- Personal characteristics:
Age, Gender, Height, Education, Employment status, Income, Life style
Physical abilities and constraints, e.g. poor eyesight, color blindness, etc.
- Task related characteristics:
Goals, Tasks, Usage, Training and experience
- Geographic and social characteristics:
Culture, Ethnical background, Location, Community

3.4.4 Main User Groups

Here are our main user groups

1. Companion
2. Supporter
3. Shopper

User Group	Percentage from Observations	Priority	Type
Companion	23%	1	Typical
Supporter	16%	2	Representative
Shoppers	41%	3	Representative

Figure 5: Main User Groups

We are going to focus mainly on Companion user group, which represents those users who are accompanying shopper, but don't aim to help him/her in the shopping process. This will be our Focus group.

4. PROTOTYPES AND IMPLEMENTATION

During the course of our project we used different types of prototyping approaches, namely storyboards, paper prototypes, Wizard of Oz and video prototyping. The following sections discuss our methods and findings in detail.

4.1 Storyboards

After we had chosen the need that we would attempt addressing and our focus groups, we started prototyping using storyboards to illustrate key points in our ideas in a usage narrative manner. The aim was to allow the user to understand the different proposals for our system. The ideas that we presented the users with are as follows.

- Eye Test/Discounts - Random short games which test eye concentration power and allow player to earn discount coupons if they win.
- Charity - Philanthropy theme based game which prompts user to donate for a good cause toward the end.
- Magic drawing - creating drawings and designs using gestures that the user can print and take along with him/her if desired
- Football - Soccer based game with options like penalty shootout.
- Virtual Me - Game that requires the player to save his avatar from being attacked by aliens.
- Snow Fight - Game where the snowman is throws snowballs at the player and the player must defend himself/herself.

To determine which idea we should build on further, we sought the opinion of our users. First, we interviewed 5 people (one female, four male). We showed the storyboard images and asked their opinion and preference. In addition to this, we devised an online questionnaire which had the storyboard images and questions similar to the ones from the interview sessions. We sent out this questionnaire to the people, in our contact circle, which could be considered to part of our focus group. We received 33 responses (21 male, 12 female). The graph in Figure 6 shows the overall

Figure 6: Overall Weighted Likability Results

weighted likability. Thus, based on these results we chose the Football idea.

4.2 Paper Prototypes

4.2.1 Cycle 1

To gauge the user's initial reaction, we created some initial sketches for the Penalty Shoot-Out option, some of which are as shown in Figure 7, for a defined user interaction path. We tried user interaction testing with the paper prototypes directly but the users were not responsive. Subsequently we used a Wizard of Oz setup by projecting the sketches on the wall in a size which was comparable to Athena's requirements, and then changing the images in accordance to the user's actions.

Figure 7: Some sketches from Paper Propotype Cycle 1

We recruited 4 people (2 male, 2 female) for the user testing none of whom were a part of the storyboard interview sessions. We briefed them about the overall goal, and told them that there is only one defined path which they can follow. After giving the instructions we allowed the users to interact with the projections. We observed and took notes about their actions. Following the testing session we interviewed them to get their feedback. Few things such as the demo or help for playing, the menu items and game messages were unclear to a majority of users.

4.2.2 Cycle 2

We re-designed for the issues pointed out by the users from Cycle 1. We then approached two of the users (1 female, 1 male) who were part of the testing session from the previous cycle and requested to engage in interacting with our system again. Before interaction they were given instructions similar to previous time.

The interview session which took place after the testing and the observation during the session showed that the problems identified in Cycle 1 were resolved. The users gave further feedback on the need for a time bar and changing certain menu options which didn't seem good.

4.2.3 Cycle 3

After adding timers as per the requirements of Athena and keeping only those menu options preferred by the users, we had another round of user interaction testing. In this cycle we included 4 participants (2 male, 2 female). The instructions given to the users were much like the ones in the previous cycles.

In addition to observing the users during interaction and interviewing them individually after the testing session, in this cycle we also held a group interview session. However, the group interview session proved to be quite useless because we couldn't draw any final conclusion and the session was dominated by the strong-minded users.

The observations and interviews gave us the impression that the exit conditions were not clearly defined for the user, and more fans and sound emotion would be better. Moreover, the game messages and scoring were not completely

understood and the users expressed their confusion regarding them.

As part of this phase, we video recorded some of our users during interaction testing (with their permission) and reached out the stakeholders in Germany i.e. the shop owner/assistants for their feedback. Unfortunately we could interview only 1 shop assistant. In general the idea was well received. However, reservations were expressed for the cracking sound which was quite alarming for the shop assistant.

We also interviewed shop owners in our home countries after showing the same video recording. The response received from them from vastly different from the feedback in Germany. The shop owners in the different nations of Armenia, India and Iran were concerned about making strange gestures in public and crowd management. Based on these interviews we understood that different countries have a different view which is influenced by their culture, and we decided to ignore the suggestions made by the stakeholders in our home countries.

4.2.4 Cycle 4

Design was revised to include exit button, different scoring board and new game messages. Four of users (3 male, 1 female) who were a part of Cycle 1 or Cycle 3 were recruited for testing using the same method as previous cycles in this phase.

The conclusions from the interview sessions were very satisfactory. The users approved of the revisions made. Nonetheless, the user observation indicated that the paper prototype failed to give the user a feeling involvement and game action.

Again we video recorded part of the testing session, and sought the opinion and feedback of the stakeholders. We were able to interview 2 male stakeholders (1 student assistant, 1 shop manager). This time also the response to the idea was good. The shop manager questioned about the how much of an investment Athena would be; upon calculation afterward the hardware cost was estimated to be ≈ 1650

4.2.5 Cycle 5

In addition to Penalty Shoot-Out option we also designed and tested for the Free Kick option. We used participatory design approach involving 2 male users for understanding what the user expects. Finally to make the sketches for the paper prototype we used the results from the participatory design and our knowledge of the golden rules for designing interfaces.

We tested this paper prototype in the same manner as before - projection and Wizard of Oz methods. For the interaction testing and interview, we recruited 5 users (4 male, 1 female) none of whom had participated in the user testing previously. We also video recorded some of the users during the interaction testing, distributed this among 3 users (2 male, 1 female) who had joined in user testing before and asked them for feedback.

The results of the testing showed that the winning conditions were not clear and appropriate changes in game messages was done to improve this.

4.3 Higher Medium Fidelity Prototype

4.3.1 Cycle 1

For allowing better interaction and game involvement, we designed for a higher fidelity prototype as shown in Figure 8. We wrote a program which would let us control the sequence of images and provide appropriate messages to the user.

Figure 8: Some screens from Higher Medium Fidelity Prototype Cycle 1

We engaged 5 users (3 female, 2 male) for the testing session, none of whom had participated before. A part self-generating testing technique was used as before with the goal of playing Penalty Shoot-Out.

The conclusions from the user observation and interviews were very positive. The new graphics and programming approach surely enhanced the immersive feel. Nonetheless, the demo was cited as a problem area that couldn't be grasped easily. In this cycle we received several good suggestions from the users such as usage of LED perimeter for store advertisement.

4.3.2 Cycle 2

The demo was improved and we conducted a hallway testing session where we could test with 5 users. Instead of conducting interviews we asked the users to fill out a questionnaire to judge our usability. More details about this are mentioned in the next section.

The voluntary verbal feedback that we got from the users in this session gave us a lot to think about. Some users wanted to go and forth in the system while others wished to choose specific opponents and uniforms for the players. We brainstormed and decided that if these need to be implemented then it should be in the form of hidden options on the screen which appear on hovering in the right location.

4.3.3 Cycle 3

As part of re-designing in this phase the menu was re-styled using Task Frequency Analysis method. For the arriving at new menu style 13 users (6 male, 7 female) were recruited. After this we incorporated Kinect with our existing program to detect the player movements. Following this another cycle of testing was done with 10 users.

The users were very satisfied with the good feedback. However, the felt that kicking the ball in a public place could

be a bit against social norms and marking on the floor indicating the safe range from the system is required. Also, they couldn't understand how the system would judge the force of their kick. Nevertheless, the overall enthusiasm and response was great!

5. STUDY OF SYSTEM USABILITY

We conducted three usability tests which are explained below.

5.1 Our Usability Results

We attempted to judge the usability, user experience and attractive quotient of our system using a post interaction questionnaire. This was done at the end of Higher Medium Fidelity Prototype Cycle 2.

The questionnaire contained 12 questions with which we gathered information about the user's understanding of the system, the game and the interaction techniques.

The results of the study show that not only were the purpose of the system and tasks clearly understood, but also most of the users found the system easy to use and navigate. There were complains about the restricted 3 minute play time. However, that is part of the requirements of Athena which was designed keeping in mind that the user should not forget his true role as a companion. Thereby, that aspect of the result was ignored. Finally we calculated the average attractiveness rating to be 4/5.

5.2 Software Usability Measurement Inventory (SUMI) Results

We reached out to 10 users who were part of Higher Medium Fidelity Prototype Cycle 3 testing, and asked them to fill out the SUMI questionnaire. The SUMI questionnaire is a standard method of calculating a system's software quality from user's perspective.

Figure 9: Athena's SUMI Results

We achieved good results with SUMI as can be seen in Figure 5.

5.3 AttrakDiff Results

AttrakDiff makes possible the evaluation of any product by users. By using AttrakDiff we were able to understand how attractive the product is in terms of usability and appearance. It was left to us to decide how long the rating sheets

Figure 10: AttrakDiff Results

were accessible to the test participants. We tested using AttrakDiff with 6 users, in the age group of 20-40. From Figure 6 it can be observed that our system borders on the desired region, which we believe is good since it is still a prototype.

6. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

Further user observation in the end of the project lead us to some new ideas for future developments. One of the problems users mentioned was the social norm problem for acting in front of the system. Another one was the users behavior in kicking imaginary ball and their different gestures. To overcome these problems, our proposal was to place a real ball in front of the users. This ball would be connected to the system in such a way that besides supporting movement in selected areas, it prevents the ball from wandering inside the shop. Using this will help users to interact with system in way that is more realistic. Feeling the kick with ball is encouraging for many people. It might encourage more users to interact and it will overcome the imaginary gesture problem and better understand the force of the kick. However, by using this idea there might be possible changes in hardware and implementations. One possible change will be capturing ball hit instead of user's movement to visualize the ball movement in the system. This is possible by using sensors that can capture the ball hit, its strength, and its direction. Initial elements that we suggest for primary prototyping are sloped surface and spring for controlling the ball movement in selected area, sensors, and a moving box, which can capture the ball hit and will be flexible enough to return the ball. This proposal needs to be studied with users. Testing with users is the best way to understand the

best solution for them.

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